

MEDICAL SCIENCES

MONITORING AND CLINICAL AND LABORATORY FEATURES OF SEVERE PNEUMONIA IN CHILDREN OF THE CITY OF PAVLODAR

Adayeva A.

resident for 2 years, specializing in infectious diseases of adults, children. Semey Medical University, Pavlodar, Republic of Kazakhstan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11199101>

Abstract

In this work, a retrospective analysis of 20 medical records of an inpatient patient from 2022 to 2023 with severe pneumonia in children was performed.

Keywords: severe course of pneumonia, fever, respiratory failure

Relevance: every year more than 17 million people in the world suffer from pneumonia, children under 5 years old are at special risk. So, according to WHO, about 150 million cases of pneumonia in the world are registered in children of this age every year, of which 20 million have severe pneumonia and require hospitalization. To date, the incidence of pneumonia has not decreased in the Republic of Kazakhstan.

The purpose of the study: to study the clinical and laboratory features of severe pneumonia in children in the Pavlodar region.

Materials and methods of the study: we conducted a retrospective analysis of 20 medical records of inpatient patients with pneumonia for 2022-2023, children who were on inpatient treatment in an infectious diseases hospital in Pavlodar.

Results and discussions: analysis of the data obtained showed that among the patients, children in the age group 0-5 years prevailed – 16 patients (80%), followed by patients aged 5-14 years – 3 patients (15%), over 14 years – 1 patient (5%)

The primary stage of our study was to study the clinical features of the course of severe pneumonia in children. At this stage, categories such as duration of fever, complications in the form of respiratory failure were assessed. According to the results of the study, the duration of fever from 3 to 7 days was observed in 17 children (85%), more than 8 days in 3 children (15%). Respiratory failure with O₂ saturation is below 93% in 19 children (95%)

The second task of our study is to study the laboratory data of children with severe pneumonia. The following indicators were taken as a basis: general blood

test, CRP, blood gases. According to the results: leukocytosis is observed in 17 children (85%), according to the leukogram, a shift to the right in 15 children (75%), an increase in the level of CRP in 15 children (75%), according to blood gases, acidosis was in 16 children (80%).

Conclusion: Comparing the medical records of patients for 2022-2023, it can be concluded that the severe course of pneumonia is still an urgent problem, prevailing at the age of 0 to 5 years. The main clinical manifestation is prolonged fever and symptoms of respiratory failure. According to laboratory data, indicators such as leukocytosis, leukogram – right shift, increased CRP in biochemical blood analysis, acidosis prevail mainly in half of children.

The outcomes and prognosis of pneumonia depend on the severity of the course, the presence of complications, and the immune status of the patient. In most cases, with timely and adequate treatment, the prognosis of pneumonia is favorable.

References:

1. "Infectious diseases in children. Protocols, diagnostics and treatment, prevention" , Kharchenko G.A., Kimirilova O.G. , 2022
2. Fundamentals of respiratory support in anesthesiology, intensive care and intensive care., Kolesnichenko A.N., Gritsan A.I.2023
3. Anesthesiology, intensive care and intensive care in children. Stepanenko S.M. 2022
4. Emergency care and intensive care in pediatrics, V.V.Lazareva. 2021